

Assessing the Impact of Commercial advertising of Domestic brands on consumer behavior

(Case Study: Electronic equipment Manufacturers)

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Abstract

Purpose – The aim of this research was Assessing the Impact of Commercial advertising of Domestic brands on consumer behavior (Case Study: Electronic equipment Manufacturers).

Design/methodology/approach – For data analysis Descriptive and inferential statistical methods of regression test were used in SPSS software. The statistical population was included the managers of active electronic equipment manufacturers in Tehran, A total of 500 people. Using the Cochran equation, the sample size was 109 people. To collect information, a researcher-made questionnaire was used, which consisted of 23 statements, whose content and face validity was confirmed by 30 experts, and its reliability in a preliminary test with 30 subjects For all the studied variables was higher than 0.7 Which is at an acceptable level.

Findings – The findings showed that Commercial advertising of domestic brands have an impact both on consumer behavior and also on its components i.e the attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control.

Keywords: Commercial advertising of domestic brands, Consumer behavior, Attitude, Subjective norm, perceived behavioral control.

Research type: research paper

Introduction

Today Attracting the customer's attention in the competitive market is harder than before and organizations Paying huge costs for advertising to achieve this goal. Traditional advertising, on the other hand, are no longer enough and organizations are always looking for newer and more innovative ways to present their brand and product. On the other hand, the issue of ethnic, national and global cultures and their future status are more important than ever. Advertising also plays an important role in developing sales and increasing market share. Companies in order to compete with competing businesses must continually remind themselves to their customer and have the first place in their minds. Otherwise, their share will be rivaled. Often, businesses that have a smaller market share or are newcomers, need more advertising than larger businesses (Kladou, Kavaratzis et al. (2017)). The reason for this is "the Process of Reaction to Advertising". Accordingly, advertising increases market share to a certain extent and after that, the sales fell due to the lack of customer returns and the lack of repeat purchases. So companies with large market share more focus on reminding their product in the customer's mind. In contrast, smaller competitors need more advertising to increase their market share. They need a high budget to raise awareness of their products and increasing sales and market share. Based on the process of reacting to the advertising of new businesses and products, they Need more investment to be

seen in the target market and maintaining this situation to realize the purchase. Sometimes it is necessary that advertising go beyond The rules and character of your product and the category in which it fits. Advertising must be inherent in nature to attract everyone to itself. As a result, it has a significant impact on customer awareness. Advertising is a means by which Customers become aware of inventions and innovations (Mpinganjira and Maduku (2019); Pnevmatikos, Vardar et al. (2018)).

On the other hand, public perception is that consumer behavior, is how to buy goods and services by individuals, But in reality, consumer behavior is more than buying goods and services by individuals. In general, consumer behavior is defined as: The final decision of the consumer, taking into account acquisition, consumption and getting rid of the goods, services, time and opinions of the various decision making sectors over a period of time. Consumer behavior is not just about buying goods, but it also includes the use of services, activities and beliefs. Activities such as traveling, going to dentistry, enrolling for classes, and so on, are All part of the consumer behavior. That's why consumer behavior, include goods, services, activities and beliefs and marketing efforts to meet the needs of individuals is called the offer (Chaney, Hosany et al. (2018)).

Although the purchase mode is very important for marketers, but consumer behavior does not only include purchases. Consumer behavior includes three activity of acquisition, Consumption and Getting rid. Acquisition refers to the process whereby a person obtains an offer. Consumption is only a one way to acquisition and obtaining a good, Cases Such as Borrowing, bartering, leasing etc are other ways that a person can acquire goods and services. Consumption is the process through which a person uses a product or service. Despite the fact that most researches on consumer behavior has studied acquiring, Consumption is the core of consumer behavior and it is important for the following reasons (Coelho, Rita et al. (2018)):

- First, the consumer of a good conveys an implicit symbolic message to others. For example, Use of a special car, the type of person's cover, Type of recreational activities, all can induce the character of person to others.
- Second, consumption can affect other people's behaviors. For example, transferring the negative experience of a consumer to others is a Factor that affects Buying or consumption of an offer from them.

Ultimately getting rid is a process in which the person gets rid of the offer he has previously acquired. Getting rid is not only involves throwing away an offer, But the exchange of an offer with another offer, Give the offer to other people, changing the Function of offer all are methods that A consumer Gets rid of his acquired goods and services (Bell and Buchner (2018)).

Consumer behavior includes Acquiring, consumption and getting rid as a dynamic sequence in a specific time period. This time period can include a few hours, days, weeks, months or even several years. Consumer behavior does not necessarily reflect the behavior of a particular person. Decision about buying a car, going to a particular restaurant, rental of housing are behaviors that can include a group of friends, a number of colleagues, or all family members. In addition, people can have several roles during doing a consumer behavior (Davvetas and Diamantopoulos (2017)).

For example, in buying a car, one or more family members may act as collectors of information, While the same person or people can also take on the role of consumer or buyer in this process. Consumer behavior includes Understand and identify the reason, location, time, quality, duration and frequency of purchase, Acquiring, consuming and getting rid of an offer. Consumers should decide on acquiring, consuming and getting rid of a product or service (Cartwright, McCormick et al. (2016), (Zenetti and Klapper 2016)). They may Save their Additional income or decide to buy housing or to throw away a good. In some cases, the decision about Acquiring, consuming and getting rid is related with consumer concern. For example, an exploratory study in eight countries showed that Getting rid of mobile phones has been relevant with the risk of brain tumors. Social, psychological, economic and other concerns can all encourage the consumer to make a decision about acquiring, consuming and getting rid of an offer (Zenetti and Klapper 2016)).

But achieving a competitive advantage in today's world, will not be achieved only by relying on the functional features of goods and services. But also in the present age, brand as a most valuable asset of a company is a distinctive feature of a business company from its rivals. Brand value develops in loyalty, Positive perceptions, Ability to attract new customers, Demanding higher prices, Ease of entry into the new market and preventing the entry of new rivals (Khalifa and Shukla (2017)). Part of the value of a brand is due to its help in entering new products and Brand development is one of the most commonly used branding strategies. To accelerate the movement and changing the consumption goods, more than 85 percent of the introduction of new products, are Brand development. Brand development, is introduction of new products, under the existing brand name and has been developed as a popular strategy since the 1980s. Brand development Affect the Original brand value and Company name, and consumer familiarity with the original brand can help in entering a new product and rapidly expanding it into newly formed market segments. Brand development strategy and extension of consumer choice to different products is doing with the aim of increasing loyalty customers, saving in time and cost of advertising and ultimately generate wealth and value added And that's why it has become one of the most popular ways of acquiring the growth (Torelli and Rodas (2017)).

Although brand development helps to create consumer acceptance of a new product, through linking new product with a well-known brand name, but the inappropriate use of this strategy may lead to the failure of new product. For example, there may be associations about the original product that wouldn't be compatible with the new product. Therefore, the use of this strategy may harm both the new product and the brand. In addition, the new product category may not fit with the original product category and this disproportionate causes the failure of new product. But companies to reduce the risk of destroying their brand image, use advertising to raise awareness of their customers and creating loyalty in them towards the brand. Advertising has always been one of the most important communication tools in marketing activities and plays a vital role and create a good brand image in the minds of customers. According to Crocker, Marketing communications and promotional activities are very important in creating value and developing brands (Mantovani, de Andrade et al. (2017)).

Many researchers believe that advertising has a positive relationship with brand development. Because advertising and promotional activities can create a strong and desirable relationship between brand and customer memory and create positive feelings and judgments about the development of a brand in the minds of the customer. When customers are exposed to the extensive and continuous advertising of a brand, Unconsciously the Sense of trust forms in them. But all these desirable effects depend both on the amount of investment and the kind of message that is being transmitted. Previous research results show that Advertising penetration can be beneficial on the attitude and behavior of the customer because commercials advertising instead of sale Advertising, Encourage customers to try out existing brands. Therefore, existing a proper relationship of company with customers as well as widespread investment in Advertising activities and the creation of affiliate marketing Not only will increase the brand value, But also significantly affect the process of decision making and consumer behavior (Chovanová, Korshunov et al. (2015)).

Therefore, given the importance of protecting domestic goods as well as the impact of marketing activities as the most important activity of the organization to maintain and protect its brand and products, this research attempts to answer this question that does Commercial advertising of Domestic brands affect the consumer behavior of Electronic Equipment Manufacturers?

I. Theoretical background

1-1. Advertising

A tool that can be used to implement a social marketing process, is using from the power of advertising. The purpose of the advertisements was to create a long term brand and it is an indirect way to change the direction of customers toward Advertisements products or services which is done by awareness about the product or service by visualizing the desired memories. One of the biggest benefits of advertising is the Ability to communicate with a large number of people at a single time. For example, in a form of mass media, a specific sponsor, paid the cost of advertising and basically in the mass (radio and television) and print (magazines and newspapers) media are being used Which naturally does not cause direct feedback from the target market. A number of organizations use advertisements as the dominant communication option. Selecting the right media and advertising messages that are consistent with the goals of communication is important in any marketing communication strategy (Amrouche and Yan (2017)).

Most advertising messages reflect a set of advantages or benefits of a product or service. Message coordination between different activities should be considered. These activities include: Content (what to say), Structure (logically how to say it), Shape (symbolically how it be) and the source (how to present it; or who is the spokesperson of the message / media). Any advertising message In order to attract the audience to the content should use a special gravity. An attraction to attract the attention of dedicated users affects people's feelings which led to outbreak of behavior about the product or service. Advertising attractions related to consumer motivation, talk about the wants, needs and stimulating their interest. Various advertising attractions are available and are precisely related to the style used to transmit the message. Advertising Attractions May be widely categorized as the informational or logical attractions and emotional attractions (Black and Veloutsou (2017)).

1-2. Brand

Various definitions of the brand are provided, and there are different approaches to these definitions. Some definitions are from a consumer point of view; some aspects are from the company's point of view and even some of the others are described in terms of the purpose they pursue. For a long time, the brand was considered only as part of a physical product and most brand definitions, Interpreted the brand as a word, name or mark. Today, Brand is something that goes beyond these issues. A brand is a collection of promises and commitments and refers to trust, stability and constancy, and a defined set of expectations (Boerman and Kruikemeier (2016)). This set of promises and commitments include Characteristics and the features that a buyer buys and its result is His satisfaction. The features

that make up a brand may be real or unrealistic, rational or emotional, tangible or invisible. However, a consumer may have no connection with a product or service but he can have some kind of relationship with the brand and its features. This relationship with the brand and its characteristics is influenced by customer perceptions and is completely mental and this relationship is the guarantor of long-term business relationship and customer buying behavior. In fact, consumers' perception of brand, whether true or false; is the basis for their decision to buy a brand. If a brand is constantly perceived as a provider of high quality standards, is considered Valuable and strong. Therefore, understanding why the authors, do not consider the Brand as a something much more or less than the set of people's mental relationships, here is determined. Strong brands in the world have a unique place in the minds of consumers and these positions almost for all people around the world are interpreted in the same way. For example, when you think of the FedEx brand, "Guaranteed Carriage" comes to your mind or when you think of Volvo, "Guaranteed Security" comes to your mind. If a product is produced for a specific function and exists in the outside world, Brand is, in fact, a meaning and concept beyond this function and is in the minds of people (Huang, Dawes et al. (2017)).

1-3. Consumer behavior

Many authors believe that the study of consumer behavior is deeply influenced by the science of psychology. On the other hand, sociologists emphasize the study of social groups in the field of consumer behavior. So theories can well help in Identifying individual characteristics, beliefs and values which are related to different health and consumption behaviors and may be changeable. Therefore, in order to understand consumer behavior, the planned behavior theory is used which is a psychosocial theory. This theory includes a study of attitudes which forms the basis of the science of psychology, And also includes groups that affect consumer behavior which is the basis of the science of sociologic. Planned Behavior Theory is based on this principle that People make reasonable and rational decisions based on accessible information (Kuvykaite and Piligrimiene (2014)).

The cornerstone of this theory is based on the assumption that the person's behavior is influenced by the individual's intention to do that. On the other hand, the intention of the person is influenced by two factors: 1) Individual motivation against behavior and 2) mental norms. The theory of planned behavior, is an attempt to explain the behaviors that does not occur entirely on purpose. Therefore, the theory of planned behavior, In addition to the two previous factors that were mentioned in the theory of reasonable behavior, adds another variable that is called Control of Planned Behavior (Huang, Dawes et al. (2017)).

1-3-1. Attitude

Attitude about a behavior is defined as a positive or negative feeling associated with behavior. Based on the theory of rational behavior theory, Attitude about a behavior is determined by individual's beliefs, the consequences of the behavior and the individual's assessment of these consequences. In other words, the attitude Points out to the Incompatible firm beliefs of a Person About doing behavior. Jin and Kang (2011) in their study of Chinese consumers concluded that the Attitudes have been the most important and best predictor of Chinese consumer purchasing intentions for foreign goods (clothing). Another study by Son and Jane (2013) also approved the impact of Indian consumers' attitudes towards the purchase of foreign branded goods. Many studies have been done in the past that showed a significant influence of attitude on consumer purchase intentions (Romaniuk and Nenycz-Thiel (2013)).

1-3-2. Subjective norm

The subjective norm is defined as the perception and imagination of the confirmation or disapproval of his behavior by others. In other words, subjective norm refers to the impact of influential individuals (reference groups) on one's behavior and performance. Influential individuals can include family members, friends, co-workers, and affiliates. Kim and Carpeva (2010), studying on a group of American students observed a direct relationship between subjective norms and purchasing intentions regarding the purchase of counterfeit branded and non-original goods. This positive relationship between the subjective norm and the intention of the purchase has been repeatedly proved in numerous studies (Jayawardhana (2013)).

1-3-3. Perceived behavioral control

Perceived behavioral control refers to the degree or severity of the perceived difficulty of a person related to doing a particular behavior. There are some behaviors that people have the intention to do them But because of the lack of opportunities or resources (such as money, time, skill, etc.) They aren't able to do them. Perceived behavioral control helps to predict these behaviors. Based on the theory of planned behavior, the more opportunities and resources an individual has to carry out an action, a person's control over his or her behavior will also be greater. Perceived behavioral control affects the intentions and behaviors of the individuals. Several studies have confirmed the significant

relationship between perceived behavioral control and purchasing intentions. Past studies have also acknowledged the direct relationship between perceived behavioral control and real shopping behavior (Merchant and Rose (2013)).

II. Research methodology

This research has been defined in order to assess the impact of Commercial advertising of domestic brands of Electronic Equipment Manufacturers on consumer behavior. In this research, to test the hypotheses about the Relationship between the Variables of Commercial advertising of domestic brands and Consumer Behavior Field data research method is used which is collected through a questionnaire. This research is in terms of purpose is Applied, in terms of method is Descriptive and in terms of time is in the type of Survey research method. Also, the present study, in terms of purpose, is an applied research and in terms of how it is done, it is placed in the Group of Surveying-correlation research. Because in this study, researcher has used the inferential statistics (regression test) to examine the effect of variables and their relationships. As the result of this study can be useful to improve the identification of consumer behavior of electronic equipment manufacturers. So in terms of purpose it Has that aspects of A Developmental - applied research. Also as this research does not consider the data associated with the lamb of the time, it is not in the type of cross-sectional research.

In order to direct the analysis path, a main hypothesis and three subsidiary ones were developed Based on identified findings in the studies conducted in the relevant research, these hypotheses are:

2-1 The main hypothesis

1. Commercial advertising of domestic brands affects consumer behavior.

2-2 Sub-hypotheses

1. Commercial advertising of domestic brands affects attitude.
2. Commercial advertising of domestic brands affects the Subjective norms.
3. Commercial advertising of domestic brands affects perceived behavioral control.

According to the above mentioned contents and the four hypotheses, the following conceptual model is presented Based on the planned behavior theory in order to understand the impact of Commercial advertising of domestic brands of Electronic equipment Manufacturers on consumer behavior:

Figure 1: The Conceptual Model of the impact of Commercial advertising of domestic brands of Electronic Equipment Manufacturers on consumer behavior

2-3 Data Collection Tool

In order to collect the required data, a researcher-made questionnaire was used. The questionnaire statements were extracted through a review of previous research. Also required content are Collected by studying books and previous

research related to the research topic and Websites and internal and external scientific articles and then with the guidance of a supervisor and a few expert comments, To analyze the research information, a Questionnaire based on the five-point Likert scale (I totally agree, I agree, I do not mind, I disagree, I totally disagree) Was prepared For distribution among relevant respondents. The questionnaire was contained 23 statements that the Variable of Commercial advertising of domestic brands with 6 statements, (Questions 1-6) and consumer behavior variable with 17 statements, (The variable of attitude with 5 statements (questions 7-11), The subjective norm variable with 6 statements (Questions 11-17) And perceived behavioral control variable with 6 statements (questions 18-23)) Were measured.

2-4 Investigating the validity of data collection tool

To assess the reliability or validity of the research scale, The Procedure for extracting components of measured variables from conducted researches and then localizing it using expert opinions and also a pilot model has been used. Accordingly, evaluation of the two features of content validity and measurement scale was in terms of a qualitative judgment. That is the questionnaire of this research had a 3 Content validity. Because components of the measured variables have taken from relevant research studies, And the questionnaire constructs are properly understood by members of the statistical sample. For this purpose, the Designed questionnaire as a Pre-test, was provided to 10 professors and experts; Then after correction and modifying some materials from them, again it provided to the 30 member of the Preliminary statistical community and according to Corrective comments of this group, the relevance of the questions was ensured according to the statistical population of the study. Finally, a final questionnaire was designed and was used for data collection.

2-5 Reliability of the data collection tool

One of the most common ways to measure reliability of the questionnaire is Cronbach's alpha coefficient which has been invented by Cronbach. The purpose of reliability of the questionnaire is that if the measured properties be Re-measured in the same way and under the same conditions and at different times almost identical Results will be achieved. Cronbach's alpha coefficients is used to measure the level of one-dimensional attitudes, ideas, and so on. In fact, we want to see to what extent the Interpretation of respondents from questions was the same. The basis of this coefficient is based on the scale. The scale is a handful of numbers which on a continuum is assigned to people, things or behaviors in order to quantify the qualities. The most commonly used scale in social researches is the Likert scale. The Likert scale is based on the assumption that the statements have a same weight. Thus some Scores will be given to each item (For example, from 1 to 5 for a 5-point Likert scale) which the sum of the scores that each person gets from the statements, will represent his tendency. Cronbach's alpha is generally calculated using one of the following relationships (Torelli and Rodas (2017)).

$$\alpha = \frac{k}{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k S_i^2}{\sigma^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

Or

$$\alpha = \frac{k\bar{C}}{\bar{V} + (k-1)\bar{C}} \quad (2)$$

Which in this relationship K is the number of questions, S_i^2 is Variance of Question i, σ^2 is Variance of total sum of questions, \bar{C} is Average covariance between questions, \bar{V} is the average variance of questions. Using the definition of Cronbach's alpha, we can conclude that: 1) whatever the positive correlation between the questions increases, Cronbach's alpha will increase and vice versa; 2) whatever the average variance of questions increases, Cronbach's alpha will decrease; 3) Increasing the number of questions will have a positive or negative impact on the Cronbach's alpha (Depending on the correlation between questions); 4) Increasing the sample size, Reduces the average variance of questions And thus increase the Cronbach Alpha. Obviously, the closer the Cronbach Alpha to one, internal consistency between questions was greater and as a result, questions will be more homogeneous. Cronbach Has suggested that the coefficient of 45% is low, 75% is moderate and acceptable, and 95% is high. Obviously, if the alpha value be low, it should be checked that by eliminating which questions, its value can be increased (Mantovani, de Andrade et al. (2017)).

In this research, using SPSS software, Cronbach's alpha was measured for research variables, whose results are presented in Table 1. The results show that the value of Cronbach's alpha for each of the four variables in this study are Higher than 0.7, and Therefore, it has an acceptable reliability.

Table 1: Cronbach's alpha for research variables

Test coefficient	Component	Variable	Type of variable
0.912	Commercial advertising of domestic brands		Independent
0.851	Attitude	Consumer behavior	Dependent
0.871	Subjective norm		
0.824	Perceived behavioral control		

2-6 Statistical society and sample

It is certain that Implementation of a research will not be possible without its territories. The statistical society in each research is all the elements and people who are common in a geographic scale (world or regional) in an industry. The statistical population of this study are include the managers of active electronic equipment companies in Tehran. Sampling is one of the most important issues in social statistics, as far as according to Ellis and Roberts, the basic concept in social statistics is the statistical society and sample. By definition, Sample is a number of people in the community whose traits are similar to those of the community and representing the community and have the integrity and harmony with the people of the community. The Cochran relationship was used to select the sample size. The Cochran relationship and its parameters are described below (Boerman and Kruikemeier (2016)):

$$n = \frac{Nt^2 pq}{\epsilon^2 (N - 1) + t^2 pq} \tag{3}$$

In this relationship, we have, n: Minimum sample size, N: Size of statistical population, t: the value of Normal variable Corresponding to a confidence level of $\alpha-1$, is considered 1.96, ϵ : Allowed error rate, equivalent to 0.05, p: Estimation of the ratio of variable Attribute and q: p-1. In this research, the statistical population are 150 people which using the Cochran equation, the Number of triable people (Statistical sample) have been evaluated Equal to 109 and these people were selected completely random and among the statistical community as statistical samples.

$$n = \frac{Nt^2 pq}{\epsilon^2 (N - 1) + t^2 pq} = \frac{150 \times 1.96 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{(0.05)^2 \times (150 - 1) + (1.96 \times 0.5 \times 0.5)} = 108.08 \approx 109 \tag{4}$$

The demographic characteristics of the statistical sample are in accordance with the data in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution and frequency percentage of triable related to demographic variables

Frequency percentage	Frequency	Variable	
79.82	87	Men	Sex
20.18	22	Women	
47.71	52	25-30	Age
31.19	34	31-35	
21.10	23	36-40	
6.42	7	Advanced Diploma	Education
69.72	76	Bachelor	
23.85	26	Master's degree	
49.54	54	1-5	Work experience
29.36	32	6-10	
14.68	16	11-15	
6.42	7	16-20	

According to Table 2 it can be expressed that Men's group with a frequency of 79.82 and the women's group with a frequency of 20.18 respectively have the highest and lowest frequency. Age group 25 to 30 years with a frequency of 47.71 and Age group 36 to 40 years with a frequency of 21.10 years have the highest and lowest frequency, respectively. In the bachelor group with a frequency of 69.72 and in the Advanced Diploma group with a frequency of 6.42 respectively have the highest and lowest frequency. In the group of 1 to 5 years with a frequency of 49.54 and in the group of 16 to 20 years with a frequency of 6.42 have the highest and lowest frequency, respectively.

III. Research results and findings

3-1. Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

Before testing the hypotheses, the Suitable type of test for testing them should be determined. Based on whether or not the collected data are normal, the type of test will be determining; In order to evaluate and assess the normality The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is uses. This test is a distribution matching test for quantitative data. If the researcher has a sample of a quantitative amounts and wants to determine that does this sample obtained from a community with normal distribution or not, he uses this test. Normality test of a distribution is one of the most common tests for small samples which the scholar doubts about its normality. For this purpose, The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is a good test. In SPSS software this test has been used to matching the four different distributions i.e. Normal, Poisson, Exponential, and Uniform. This method is based on the difference between the relative cumulative frequencies of observations with Expected value under the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis states that the selected sample has a normal distribution (Poisson, exponential, or uniform) (Bell and Buchner (2018)). Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for distribution matching, Compares Cumulative probabilities of values in the data set with the cumulative probabilities of the same quantities in a certain theoretical distribution. If the difference be large enough, this test will show that the data are not consistent with one of the theoretical distributions. In this test, if the significance level be less than 5% the null hypothesis is rejected That is, data cannot have a specific distribution, such as Normal, Poisson, Exponential, or Uniform. In this study, to investigate the normality of the data of the research variables, The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used. Therefore, the null hypothesis and argument is presented in the following form (Mantovani, de Andrade et al. (2017)):

- Null hypothesis, Error greater than 0.05, If, in the value of the parameter of significance coefficient or decision criterion, the error be greater than 0.05, this indicates that the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no reason to rejecting the hypothesis that the desired sample is obtained from the normal distribution and distribution of the relevant variable data is normal.
- Argument hypothesis, Error less than 0.05, if, in the value of the parameter of significance coefficient or decision criterion, the error be less than 0.05, this indicates that the Argument hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is no reason to accepting the hypothesis that the desired sample is obtained from the normal distribution and distribution of the relevant variable data is not normal.

Results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for variables of this study are presented in the Table 3.

Table 3: The result of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test

Test result	significance level	Test coefficient	Component	Variable
Data have the normal distribution	0.62	1.58	Commercial advertising of domestic brands	Consumer behavior
	0.57	1.93	Attitude	
	0.85	2.68	Subjective norm	
	0.67	2.11	Perceived behavioral control	

Output of statistical software regarding normality of distribution of the Commercial advertising of domestic brands and Consumer behavior (attitude, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control) variables Show that at a significance level of 5%, the argument hypothesis is rejected and the data have a normal distribution.

3-2. Hypotheses Test

Main hypothesis: Commercial advertising of domestic brands affects consumer behavior. In order to test this hypothesis, a One-variable regression test was used the results of which are presented below.

Table 4: Coefficients of processing the regression model for the main hypothesis

Result	Dependent Variable: Consumer behavior				Independent variable
	Significance level	t statistics	Standard deviation of coefficients	Coefficients	
Acceptance of argument hypothesis	0.000	36.91	0.078	2.886	Intercept
	0.000	4.58	0.027	0.125	Commercial advertising of domestic brands
20.975			F statistics	Analysis of variance	Test
0.000			Significance level of F statistics		
0.55			The coefficient of determination	Ability to explain	
0.53			Adjusted coefficient of determination		
2.098			Durbin-Watson statistics	Error Independence	

The significance level of the F statistics ($Sig = 0/000 < 0/05$) was Less than 5% and it shows that the hypothesis is accepted with 95% confidence and There is a significant relationship between Commercial advertising of domestic brands and Consumer behavior. Also, with respect to the determination coefficient (0.55), it can be said that the proposed model is fitted with high accuracy and on the other hand, the amount of adjusted determination coefficient (0.53), attests to the fact that Independent variables account for about 53% of variations in dependent variables. As the Durbin-Watson statistics (2.098) is between 1.5 and 2.5, so it can be concluded that there is no Serial correlation problem in error terms of the regression between variables. Significance Levels of the Independent Variable Coefficient i.e Commercial advertising of domestic brands Show that this independent variable in the presented regression model have an effect on the dependent variable of consumer behavior. On the other hand, the significance level of the Intercept shows that the regression model also has an Intercept. On the other hand, the coefficients of Intercept (2.886) and Commercial advertising of domestic brands (0.125) have been reported with a positive sign and shows a direct relationship between these coefficients and the dependent variable.

First sub-hypothesis: Commercial advertising of domestic brands affects attitudes.

In order to test this hypothesis a One-variable regression test is used, the results of which are presented below:

Table 5: Coefficients of processing the regression model for the First sub-hypothesis

Result	Dependent Variable: attitude				Independent variable
	Significance level	t statistics	Standard deviation of coefficients	Coefficients	
Acceptance of argument hypothesis	0.000	68.886	0.045	3.109	Intercept
	0.002	3.125	0.049	0.153	Commercial advertising of domestic brands
9.767			F statistics	Analysis of variance	Test
0.000			Significance level of F statistics		
0.27			The coefficient of determination	Ability to explain	
0.24			Adjusted coefficient of determination		
2.108			Durbin-Watson statistics	Error Independence	

The significance level of F statistics ($Sig = 0/000 < 0/05$) was Less than 5% and it shows that The hypothesis is accepted with 95% confidence And There is a significant relationship between the commercial advertising of domestic brands and attitudes. Also according to the coefficient of determination (0.27) it can be said that the proposed model is fitted with high precision. On the other hand, value of the adjusted coefficient of determination (0.24) attests to the fact that the Independent variables account for about 24% of variations in dependent variables. As the Durbin-Watson statistics (2.108) is between 1.5 and 2.5, so it can be concluded that there is no Serial correlation problem in error terms of the regression between variables. Significance Levels of the Independent Variable Coefficient i.e. Commercial advertising of domestic brands Show that this independent variable in the presented regression model have an effect on the dependent variable i.e. attitude. On the other hand, the significance level of the Intercept shows that the regression model also has an Intercept. On the other hand, the coefficients of Intercept (3.109) and Commercial advertising of domestic brands (0.153) have been reported with a positive sign and shows a direct relationship between these coefficients and the dependent variable.

Second sub-hypothesis: Commercial advertising of domestic brands affects subjective norm.

In order to test this hypothesis a One-variable regression test is used, the results of which are presented below:

Table 6: Coefficients of processing the regression model for the Second sub-hypothesis

Result	Dependent Variable: subjective norm				Independent variable
	Significance level	t statistics	Standard deviation of coefficients	Coefficients	
Acceptance of argument hypothesis	0.000	33.474	0.092	3.066	Intercept
	0.07	1.818	0.04	0.072	Commercial advertising of domestic brands
3.306			F statistics	Analysis of variance	Test
0.000			Significance level of F statistics		
0.37			The coefficient of determination	Ability to explain	
0.34			Adjusted coefficient of determination		
2.097			Durbin-Watson statistics	Error Independence	

The significance level of F statistics ($Sig = 0/000 < 0/05$) was Less than 5% and it shows that The hypothesis is accepted with 95% confidence And There is a significant relationship between the commercial advertising of domestic brands and subjective norm. Also according to the coefficient of determination (0.37) it can be said that the proposed model is fitted with high precision. On the other hand, value of the adjusted coefficient of determination (0.34) attests to the fact that the Independent variables account for about 24% of variations in dependent variables. As the Durbin-Watson statistics (2.097) is between 1.5 and 2.5, so it can be concluded that there is no Serial correlation problem in error terms of the regression between variables. Significance Levels of the Independent Variable Coefficient i.e. Commercial advertising of domestic brands Show that this independent variable in the presented regression model have an effect on the dependent variable i.e subjective norm. On the other hand, the significance level of the Intercept shows that the regression model also has an Intercept. On the other hand, the coefficients of Intercept (3.066) and Commercial advertising of domestic brands (0.072) have been reported with a positive sign and shows a direct relationship between these coefficients and the dependent variable.

Third sub-hypothesis: Commercial advertising of domestic brands affects Perceived behavioral control.

In order to test this hypothesis a One-variable regression test is used, the results of which are presented below:

Table 7: Coefficients of processing the regression model for the Second sub-hypothesis

Result	Dependent Variable: Perceived behavioral control				Independent variable
	Significance level	t statistics	Standard deviation of coefficients	Coefficients	
Acceptance of argument hypothesis	0.000	20.915	0.095	1.99	Intercept
	0.000	13.315	0.024	0.326	Commercial advertising of domestic brands
177.29			F statistics	Analysis of variance	Test
0.000			Significance level of F statistics		
0.41			The coefficient of determination	Ability to explain	
0.39			Adjusted coefficient of determination		
2.250			Durbin-Watson statistics	Error Independence	

The significance level of F statistics ($Sig = 0/000 < 0/05$) was Less than 5% and it shows that The hypothesis is accepted with 95% confidence And There is a significant relationship between the commercial advertising of domestic brands and Perceived behavioral control. Also according to the coefficient of determination (0.41) it can be said that the proposed model is fitted with high precision. On the other hand, value of the adjusted coefficient of determination (0.39) attests to the fact that the Independent variables account for about 24% of variations in dependent variables. As the Durbin-Watson statistics (2.250) is between 1.5 and 2.5, so it can be concluded that there is no Serial correlation problem in error terms of the regression between variables. Significance Levels of the Independent Variable Coefficient i.e. Commercial advertising of domestic brands Show that this independent variable in the presented regression model have an effect on the dependent variable i.e. Perceived behavioral control. On the other hand, the significance level of the Intercept shows that the regression model also has an Intercept. On the other hand, the coefficients of Intercept (1.99) and Commercial advertising of domestic brands (0.326) have been reported with a positive sign and shows a direct relationship between these coefficients and the dependent variable.

IV. Conclusions

Advertising activities can be categorized as factors that Affect Brand Strength and Have a close relationship with brand equity. Today, many companies have realized that to maintain the value and develop their brand in comparison with competitors and to communicate with their customers and reducing the risk of losing markets, they have to strengthen their marketing communications, and have a good mix promotion and Use promotional and activities Such as commercial Advertising as a defensive shield. The purpose of many Advertising activities is increasing the consumer awareness and creating additional incentive to buy and influencing the consumer shopping behavior Which causes Stimulating and Quick Response in the sale. Advertising is one of the variables that a company can use to increasing the consumer awareness and knowledge in order to change their response to brand development. In general, the use of advertising increases the chances of brand development acceptance. Some researchers believe that providing information about brand development, correlates with brand associations and its goals. This information can moderate the effect of brand image on Attitudes towards brand development Provided that Companies use advertising that

properly combine brand associations with associations of new group. Consumers are looking forward to make significant All the information they receive, whether this information are in line with their expectations or not. In this process, the consumer will be likely to remember its stored brand associations which these associations will facilitate the Assessment of provided information and new product.

In this research, using a researcher-made questionnaire containing 23 statements and gathering the views of 109 managers of active electronic equipment companies in Tehran, the effects of Commercial advertising of domestic brand on consumer behavior were investigated and the following results were obtained.

First sub-hypothesis: Commercial advertising of domestic brands affects attitudes. In order to test this hypothesis a One-variable regression test is used. The significance level of F statistics () was Less than 5% and it shows that The hypothesis is accepted with 95% confidence and There is a significant relationship between the commercial advertising of domestic brands and attitudes. Also according to the coefficient of determination (0.27) it can be said that the proposed model is fitted with high precision. On the other hand, value of the adjusted coefficient of determination (0.24) attests to the fact that the Independent variables account for about 24% of variations in dependent variables. As the Durbin-Watson statistics (2.108) is between 1.5 and 2.5, so it can be concluded that there is no Serial correlation problem in error terms of the regression between variables. Significance Levels of the Independent Variable Coefficient i.e. Commercial advertising of domestic brands Show that this independent variable in the presented regression model have an effect on the dependent variable i.e. attitude. On the other hand, the significance level of the Intercept shows that the regression model also has an Intercept. On the other hand, the coefficients of Intercept (3.109) and Commercial advertising of domestic brands (0.153) have been reported with a positive sign and shows a direct relationship between these coefficients and the dependent variable.

Second sub-hypothesis: Commercial advertising of domestic brands affects subjective norm. In order to test this hypothesis a One-variable regression test is used. The significance level of F statistics () was Less than 5% and it shows that The hypothesis is accepted with 95% confidence and There is a significant relationship between the commercial advertising of domestic brands and subjective norm. Also according to the coefficient of determination (0.37) it can be said that the proposed model is fitted with high precision. On the other hand, value of the adjusted coefficient of determination (0.34) attests to the fact that the Independent variables account for about 24% of variations in dependent variables. As the Durbin-Watson statistics (2.097) is between 1.5 and 2.5, so it can be concluded that there is no Serial correlation problem in error terms of the regression between variables. Significance Levels of the Independent Variable Coefficient i.e. Commercial advertising of domestic brands Show that this independent variable in the presented regression model have an effect on the dependent variable i.e. subjective norm. On the other hand, the significance level of the Intercept shows that the regression model also has an Intercept. On the other hand, the coefficients of Intercept (3.066) and Commercial advertising of domestic brands (0.072) have been reported with a positive sign and shows a direct relationship between these coefficients and the dependent variable.

Third sub-hypothesis: Commercial advertising of domestic brands affects Perceived behavioral control. In order to test this hypothesis a One-variable regression test is used. The significance level of F statistics () was Less than 5% and it shows that The hypothesis is accepted with 95% confidence And There is a significant relationship between the commercial advertising of domestic brands and Perceived behavioral control. Also according to the coefficient of determination (0.41) it can be said that the proposed model is fitted with high precision. On the other hand, value of the adjusted coefficient of determination (0.39) attests to the fact that the Independent variables account for about 24% of variations in dependent variables. As the Durbin-Watson statistics (2.250) is between 1.5 and 2.5, so it can be concluded that there is no Serial correlation problem in error terms of the regression between variables. Significance Levels of the Independent Variable Coefficient i.e. Commercial advertising of domestic brands Show that this independent variable in the presented regression model have an effect on the dependent variable i.e Perceived behavioral control. On the other hand, the significance level of the Intercept shows that the regression model also has an Intercept. On the other hand, the coefficients of Intercept (1.99) and Commercial advertising of domestic brands (0.326) have been reported with a positive sign and shows a direct relationship between these coefficients and the dependent variable.

References

- [1.] Amrouche, N. and R. Yan (2017). "National brand's local advertising and wholesale-price incentive under prior versus no prior information." Industrial marketing management **64**: 161-174.
- [2.] Bell, R. and A. Buchner (2018). "Positive effects of disruptive advertising on consumer preferences." Journal of Interactive Marketing **41**: 1-13.

- [3.] Black, I. and C. Veloutsou (2017). "Working consumers: Co-creation of brand identity, consumer identity and brand community identity." Journal of Business Research **70**: 416-429.
- [4.] Boerman, S. C. and S. Kruikemeier (2016). "Consumer responses to promoted tweets sent by brands and political parties." Computers in human behavior **65**: 285-294.
- [5.] Cartwright, J., et al. (2016). "Consumers' emotional responses to the Christmas TV advertising of four retail brands." Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services **29**: 82-91.
- [6.] Chaney, I., et al. (2018). "Size does matter: Effects of in-game advertising stimuli on brand recall and brand recognition." Computers in Human Behavior **86**: 311-318.
- [7.] Chovanová, H. H., et al. (2015). "Impact of Brand on Consumer Behavior." Procedia Economics and Finance **34**: 615-621.
- [8.] Coelho, P. S., et al. (2018). "On the relationship between consumer-brand identification, brand community, and brand loyalty." Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services **43**: 101-110.
- [9.] Davvetas, V. and A. Diamantopoulos (2017). "'Regretting your brand-self?' The moderating role of consumer-brand identification on consumer responses to purchase regret." Journal of Business Research **80**: 218-227.
- [10.] Huang, A., et al. (2017). "Consumer response to price changes in higher-priced brands." Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services **39**: 1-10.
- [11.] Jayawardhana, J. (2013). "Direct-to-consumer advertising and consumer welfare." International Journal of Industrial Organization **31**(2): 164-180.
- [12.] Khalifa, D. and P. Shukla (2017). "Me, my brand and I: Consumer responses to luxury brand rejection." Journal of Business Research **81**: 156-162.
- [13.] Kladou, S., et al. (2017). "The role of brand elements in destination branding." Journal of Destination Marketing & Management **6**(4): 426-435.
- [14.] Kuvykaite, R. and Z. Piligrimiene (2014). "Consumer engagement into brand equity creation." Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences **156**: 479-483.
- [15.] Mantovani, D., et al. (2017). "How motivations for CSR and consumer-brand social distance influence consumers to adopt pro-social behavior." Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services **36**: 156-163.
- [16.] Merchant, A. and G. M. Rose (2013). "Effects of advertising-evoked vicarious nostalgia on brand heritage." Journal of Business Research **66**(12): 2619-2625.
- [17.] Mpinganjira, M. and D. K. Maduku (2019). "Ethics of mobile behavioral advertising: Antecedents and outcomes of perceived ethical value of advertised brands." Journal of Business Research **95**: 464-478.
- [18.] Pnevmatikos, N., et al. (2018). "When should a retailer invest in brand advertising?" European Journal of Operational Research **267**(2): 754-764.
- [19.] Romaniuk, J. and M. Nenycz-Thiel (2013). "Behavioral brand loyalty and consumer brand associations." Journal of Business Research **66**(1): 67-72.
- [20.] Torelli, C. J. and M. A. Rodas (2017). "Tightness-looseness: Implications for consumer and branding research." Journal of Consumer Psychology **27**(3): 398-404.
- [21.] Zenetti, G. and D. Klapper (2016). "Advertising effects under consumer heterogeneity—the moderating role of brand experience, advertising recall and attitude." Journal of Retailing **92**(3): 352-372.